

Insights on how to tailor the properties of eco-friendly alternatives to magnesia-chromium aggregates

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ABSTRACT

On the rising demand for eco-friendly refractories, challenges remain to be addressed, such as reducing the use of chromium-based aggregates. In this sense, Borges et al. proposed Cr-free alternative compositions through a compositionally complex design approach. However, the spinel precipitates' size and morphology differed significantly through the four proposed systems. In one case, the spinel was generated as a needle-like structure, whereas in the others, spherical-like precipitates with fine diameters were obtained. Although central, the reasons for generating these distinct morphologies remained unclear. Thus, this study focused on understanding the mechanisms acting in the exsolution of distinct spinels from periclase. SEM/EBSD unveiled the similarity between both crystal structures resulting in the formation of spinel precipitates with the same crystallographic orientation as the MgO matrix. As confirmed by XRD, the distinct spinel morphology could be assigned to its lattice misfit in relation to the periclase. Moreover, for low misfit systems, the spinel is quickly exsolved along the lower energy planes of the MgO ($\{100\}$ planes) during the cooling of the system, as highlighted by dilatometric analyses. Thus, this work showed how adjustments of the spinel and/or periclase compositions could allow their microstructure designing, enabling a property-driven material selection.

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